

Recommended next steps.

Research Institution management should take responsibility for establishing an RDM organisation in their institution, including:

- clear division of responsibilities within the organisation
- resources towards and establishment of RDM education and training (look towards industry for inspiration on how to set up data steward training)
- resources towards and establishment of RDM support at several levels of the organisation (determine what type of support is needed at which level)
- prioritize RDM initiatives
- a high level implementation plan and an institutional policy
- creation of professional career tracks within data management
- ensure project funding includes budget for data management
- reward FAIR RDM at the same level as PhD awards
- recognize RDM activity as high research quality when hiring and promoting staff

Ministry/Agency for Higher education and science should support research institutions in the implementation of FAIR RDM through:

- Continuous, institution level funding for RDM initiatives, so it is not solely grant based
- Adopting the European Commission's proposed reform on research assessment as the standard for Danish universities
- Making resources available for universities to employ data stewards
- Requirements on FAIR for institutions providing research data
- Creating a common nordic training for data managers / data stewardship
- Supporting the creation of a national data stewardship network
- Allocating resources for RDM education

DeiC specifically is recommended to create infrastructure for easy sharing on the national level with FAIR as default.

Funding agencies can mainly support by making clear requirements for FAIR RDM in funded projects while supporting through funding. Beside requirements on the management of project generated research data, funders should, when appropriate, require training of early career researchers within the programs. Budgets for larger funded projects could also potentially include the hiring of a data steward. A culture change can be supported by funding agencies, as well as all other stakeholders, including RDM experience when assessing proposals.

Researchers have an important responsibility of getting acquainted with basic concepts and good practice within RDM. **Supervisors** of students and early career researchers should further take on the role of making sure to pass on this knowledge and good practices.

Journals are recommended to require data to be published along with articles.